

Deliverable D3.1 – Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection

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¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of tables	3
List of figures	3
Acronyms & abbreviations	4
Introduction.....	5
1. Content of WP3	6
2. Case study selection.....	7
2.1 Selection criteria	10
3. Focusing the research	11
4. Methodological guidelines for task activities.....	13
4.1. Case studies of Female led Innovations in farming and rural areas (T3.2)	13
4.2 Innovation Ambassador Selection (T3.2)	14
4.3 Assessment of Case studies (T3.3).....	14
4.4. Comparative analysis of the case studies by country and sustainability innovation dimension (T3.4).....	15
5. WP3 Data management Plan.....	17
5.1 Data management research guidelines and thematic selection (Task 3.1).....	17
5.2 Data management case studies and assessment (Task 3.2- Task 3.3).....	18
5.3 Data management Comparative analysis (Task 3.4).....	20
6. WP3 Ethical aspects	21
6.1 Procedures and criteria used to identify research participants	21
6.2 Informed consent procedures.....	22
6.3 Processing and management of personal data	23
7. Fair data	24
Annex 1. Interview guidelines	26
Annex 1.1 Interview GUIDE Rural Innovations.....	27
Annex 1.2 Interview Guide FARM Innovations.....	30

Annex 2. Index case studies report on rural innovation	35
Annex 3. Index case studies report on farms innovation.....	38
Annex 4. Index comparative report	41
Annex 5. Instruction for textual referencing and annex to case study	44
Annex 6. Fact sheet template	45
Annex 7. Project information sheet template.....	47
Annex 8. Consent form template.....	48

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Tasks, Deliverables and Timings.....	6
Table 2. Partners involved in WP3.....	7
Table 3. Country case studies and Number of interviews – Farm innovation	8
Table 4. Country case studies and Number of interviews – Rural innovation	8
Table 5. Template for the selection of the interviewees for each case study	9
Table 6. Excel sheet to support the selection of the sample.....	10
Table 7. Partners by macro regional groups	16
Table 8. Data *T3.1 description.....	18
Table 9. Data *T3.2-T3.3 description	19
Table 10. Primary Data *T3.2- T3.3 description	19
Table 11. Data *T3.4 description.....	20
Table 12. List of Interview (Template).....	44

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Overview of WP3	5
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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CO	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EB	Executive Board
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
Project Partners	
Galway	UNIVERSITY OF GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN S LINK CLG
UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POURLE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HOGSKOLAN FOR LARANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JONKOPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

INTRODUCTION

This deliverable details the Work Package (WP3) methodology. It provides a description of the research guidelines to be used in each task to achieve the aims and objectives of WP3. It contains the approach to themes and case study selection, the approach to analysis of case studies, comparative analysis approach; furthermore, it includes timelines and specific guidelines for data management.

The starting point of this deliverable is the initial case study assessment and selection framework (T1.3 - D1.4) which aims to integrate the insights gained from the FLIARA Conceptual Framework and the FLIARA Knowledge Review, along with the findings generated in WP 2, the Envisioning Process.

The aims of this deliverable are:

- to coordinate the research activities foreseen in the four tasks of WP3 into an integrated whole to ensure and increase overall rigor of the research.
- to establish common procedures for data collection to guarantee consistency of data.
- to establish strategies for adapting the implementation of methods to take into account local characteristics.
- to formulate protocols for data management.

Figure 1. Overview of WP3

1. CONTENT OF WP3

The Work Package has the following general objective:

- Deepen understanding of the pathways to success and the challenges facing female-led sustainability innovation in a) farming and b) rural areas.

This objective will be reached through the following sub-objectives:

- Develop the methodology for case study execution and identify the sustainability innovation themes to use for case study selection.
- Identify female-led innovators within the case studies, who will act as Innovation Ambassadors for the FLIARA Project
- Analysis of female-led sustainability innovation case studies and comparative analysis based on the assessment.

These objectives are met through the contribution of **four tasks**.

- T3.1 includes the preparation of the Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection. The starting point is D1.4 “Initial Case study Assessment and Selection Framework” which sets the guidelines for the FLIARA case studies.
- T3.2 is about conducting 20 case studies of women-led innovations in farming and rural areas in 9 different countries (a total of 200 interviews) and selecting 20 Innovation Ambassadors.
- T3.3 is the analysis of the case studies through a content analysis of the empirical data.
- T3.4 entails a comparative analysis of the case studies by sustainability dimension.

Participants, deliverables and timeframe for each task is indicated in Table 1.

Table 1. Tasks, Deliverables and Timings

Task	Lead Partner	Participants	Duration	Deliverable and timing
3.1	UNICAL and LNU	All partners	July 2023-December 2023	D3.1 Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection; due by December 2023 D3.2 Inventory of female-led innovations due by December 2023
3.2	UNICAL and LNU	All partners	January 2023-June 2024	D3.3 Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and 200 Fact Sheets on Female Innovations due by June 2024
3.3	UNICAL and LNU	All partners	January 2023-June 2024	
3.4	UNICAL and LNU	All partners	September 2023-December 2024	D3.4 Comparative analysis report due by December 2024 D3.5 Practice Abstracts – batch 1 due by December 2024

The WP3 starts in July 2023 and end in December 2024.

WP3 is resourced with 85.50 person months. The distribution of person months among participants is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Partners involved in WP3.

No	Partner name	Partner short name	Country	Person months
1	University of Galway	GALWAY	Ireland	6.00
2	Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	Netherland	6.00
3	Teagasc - Agriculture and Food Development Authority	TEAGASC	Ireland	3.50
4	Università Della Calabria	UNICAL	Italy	12.00
5	Longford Women's Link Clg	LWL	Ireland	4.00
6	Turun Yliopisto	UTU	Finland	2.00
7	Univerza V Ljubljani	UL	Slovenia	6.00
8	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation SI	CE	Spain	6.00
9	Hochschule Fur Nachhaltige Entwicklung Eberswalde	HNEE	Germany	6.00
10	Association Europeenne Leader Pourle Developpement Rural	ELARD	Belgium	4.00
11	Oulun Yliopisto	UOULU	Finland	6.00
12	Stiftelsen Hogskolan I Jonkoping	JU	Sweden	4.00
13	Reseau Europeen Pour Des Initiatives Communautaires Sur Les Changements Climatiques Et Le Developpement Durable	ECOLISE	Belgium/ covering Romania	4.00
14	Mendelova Univerzita V Brne	MENDELU	Czechia	6.00
15	Linneuniversitetet	LNU	Sweden	10.00

2. CASE STUDY SELECTION

The FLIARA project will carry out 20 case studies. 10 case studies will concern female-led innovations in farming and will be conducted in 9 countries (WP3a) and 10 will concern female-led innovations in rural areas and will be conducted in 10 countries (WP3b). The case studies cover different thematic areas corresponding to four sustainability dimensions (environmental, economic, social and cultural), and are conducted in four regions (Atlantic, Central and Eastern Europe, Nordic Baltic and the Mediterranean as defined in Table 3-4).

All partners except Ireland and Romania are to perform one case study on farm innovations and one case study on rural innovations. Ireland is to perform an additional case study on farm innovations while Romania is to perform only one case study on rural innovations.

Each national case study foresees 10 interviews with women leading innovation in farming (except Ireland, which will conduct 20 interviews) and 10 interviews with women leading innovation in rural areas (except Romania).

Table 3. Country case studies and Number of interviews – Farm innovation

Thematic areas covered	Country Case Studies									
	Atlantic			Central and Eastern		Nordic Baltic		Mediterranean		Total Interviews by Theme
	Ireland	Netherlands	Germany	Czech Republic	Slovenia	Sweden	Finland	Spain	Italy	
Environmental	6	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	30
Economic	6	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	30
Social	6	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	30
Cultural	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
Total Interviews per Country	20	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	100

Table 4. Country case studies and Number of interviews – Rural innovation

Thematic areas covered	Country Case Studies										
	Atlantic			Central and Eastern			Nordic Baltic		Mediterranean		Total Interviews by Theme
	Ireland	Netherlands	Germany	Czech Republic	Slovenia	Romania	Sweden	Finland	Spain	Italy	
Environmental	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	30
Economic	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	30
Social	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	30
Cultural	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
Total Interviews per Country	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	100

The process of selection is organised in five steps:

- 1) Each partner provides an inventory of female-led innovations in rural areas and in farming through a desktop analysis. This results in a long list of practices/projects illustrating the variability of female-led innovation in relation to one sustainability dimension (environmental, economic, social and cultural)

and to a typology of area (rural village, rural remote area, rural area close to city). This inventory is integrated with the results of a survey promoted by ELARD and ECOLISE. In total 530 cases of women-led innovations were collected. Deliverable 3.2 – “Inventory of female-led innovations” lays out how the process of producing the long-list by the FLIARA partners.

- 2) Each partner selects the interviewees from the long list. In addition to the typology of rural areas and the sustainability dimensions, there are also additional selection criteria (laid out in Deliverable 1.4), that the partners in each country have to consider when handing in their proposed sample. Each partner needs to select a second option either if the first case selected for a specific typology of area and sustainability dimension is unavailable or unwilling to participate in the research. The sampling template is laid out in Table 5 below.
- 3) UNICAL examines the proposed sample and matches it with the selection criteria laid out in Deliverable 1.4, aligning it to the variability of rural areas and to the four dimensions of sustainability.
- 4) Based on the results of the previous phase, the partners select their final sample.
- 5) The final sample is approved by partners and by the Executive Board.

The selection of case studies is a milestone (MS2) of WP3 and is due by the end December 2023.

Table 5. Template for the selection of the interviewees for each case study

Thematic areas covered	Typology of Area	First option – Interviewees (indicate the number in your excel sheet)	Second option – Interviewees (indicate the number in your excel sheet)
1.Environmental	Remote Rural		
2.Environmental	Rural Villages		
3.Environmental	Rural Close to City		
1.Economic	Remote Rural		
2.Economic	Rural Villages		
3.Economic	Rural Close to City		
1.Social	Remote Rural		
2.Social	Rural Villages		
3.Social	Rural Close to City		
1.Cultural	Any context (please indicate)		

2.1 SELECTION CRITERIA

The criteria for the selection of the interviewees were established in Deliverable 1.4 “Initial Guidelines for Case Study Assessment and Selection”.

In summary, four categories need to be considered:

1. The Rural Context
2. Women-Led and Inclusive
3. Innovative
4. Sustainability Practice

Each category is described in detail in D1.4.

To make sure that the partners consider all the criteria listed in D1.4, an excel file is provided (Table 6).

In addition to these criteria, the following indications have to be considered:

- 1) The focus should be on women working/living **in** rural areas; this does not include women living in urban areas and promoting innovations that benefit the rural. Hence, the specific living location of the innovator is deemed important to assess how the innovation pathways take place.
- 2) The target should be on innovations happening **on** the farm, and not innovations for the farm.

Table 6. Excel sheet to support the selection of the sample.

Sustainability Sub-themes	First Option - Interviewees	Rural Area Typology	Age Diversity	Economic Background	Ethnic and Cultural Diversity	Education Levels	Family status	Community Roles	Contextual relevance	Diversity of Innovation	Potential for Social Impact	Novelty and Creativity	Impact on Rural Development	Community benefits	Second option interviewees
Environment		Remote area													
Environment		Close to city													
Environment		Rural Village													
Economic		Remote area													
Economic		Close to city													
Economic		Rural Village													
Social		Remote area													
Social		Close to city													
Social		Rural Village													
Cultural		Please indicate													

3. FOCUSING THE RESEARCH

FLIARA aims to shine a spotlight on female led innovation. According to the FLIARA Conceptual Framework (D1.1), this means understanding the pathways to success and the challenges that women promoting sustainability innovation face in agricultural and rural areas.

Therefore, the research problem, the starting point and overall focus, which drives the WP3 research activities, may be formulated as:

“Rural women’s employment opportunities and contributions to innovation have been overshadowed, and often marginalised/silenced. There is an inadequate and inequitable rural future.”

The FLIARA framework recognises that women-led **innovation pathways** comprise a number of stages. Women-led innovations are motivated by the current realities of rural areas. These realities often lead to the decision to act, to innovate and to prepare the construction of concrete innovations. These concrete innovations often have an impact on the contexts in which they are implemented and practiced.

Secondly, the framework recognises that women-led innovation is created and developed within **innovation ecosystems** that can hinder or support female-led innovation journeys throughout their different phases. FLIARA utilises the PESTE (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, and Environmental) framework to analyse the innovation eco-systems.

Thirdly, female-led innovations can have an incremental, disruptive, sustainable and radical impact on gender (in)equality and rural sustainability. Women-led innovations can spread through different forms of **mainstreaming**. Hence, there are different ways in which they can impact society.

The following research questions provide the focus and basis for operationalisation of the WP3 research.

Four levels of questions can be distinguished in relation to the three themes considered in the FLIARA Assessment Framework (D1.4)

Level 1: Overall /core question

How do women promote innovation in rural areas and in farming? (main research questions)

Level two: Exploration of Innovation pathways

What motivates women to initiate innovation in a rural and a farm context? (Motivations for innovation)

How do women act and seek support and resources to implement innovation in rural area and farming? (Idea and preparation)

Which concrete innovations are developed for each dimension of sustainability? Which are the tangible outcomes of these innovations? (Concrete innovations)

Which are the impacts in terms of rural sustainability and gender equality? (Impact)

Level three: Innovation Ecosystem

How does the rural local context favour and obstruct female-led innovation in rural area and in farming? (Rural context conditions)

How and how well can political factors (e.g. government policies, regulations, local institutions facilitate or hinder female-led innovation journeys? (Political-institutional aspects)

How do economic conditions influence women's decisions to innovate? Which economic incentives can facilitate the expansion of viable female-led innovation journeys? (Economic aspects)

How and how well can social factors (e.g. cultural norms, gender roles, community support, social networks) facilitate or hinder female-led innovation journeys? (Socio-cultural aspects)

How and how well technological factors (e.g. availability of technology, digital infrastructure, communication tools and access to information) can facilitate or hinder female-led innovation journeys? (Technological aspects)

How and how well do environmental factors (e.g. natural resources, climate conditions, environmental sustainability) influence the type of innovations promoted by women in rural areas and in farming? How and how well do women address environmental degradation and protect and improve ecosystems in rural areas? (Environmental aspects)

Level four: Mainstreaming actions

How can successful women-led innovations be scaled up to create broader and systemic change? (Scaling potential).

Has there been a change in laws, policies, institutions or norms in relation to a successful innovation or how can the positive results of women-led innovations support this change? (Scaling-up).

Has there been a geographical replication or a broadening of the range or scope of a successful innovation? Do women collaborate with local communities/organisations to replicate and adapt their innovations to different rural contexts? Or can the positive results of women-led innovations support such collaborations? (Scaling-Out).

Are there capacity-building programmes, fundings or technical support for women to help them implement their innovations locally? (Scaling-Down).

Do organisations and institutions have the capacity to deliver and support women-led rural innovations? Do advisory services and Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Systems (AKIS) support women-led innovations? Have the practices and values of organisations and institutions been changed by women-led innovations? (Scaling-in).

Have societal values and behaviours changed through women-led innovations? (Scaling Deep).

4. METHODOLOGICAL GUIDELINES FOR TASK ACTIVITIES

4.1. CASE STUDIES OF FEMALE LED INNOVATIONS IN FARMING AND RURAL AREAS (T3.2)

The task is led by UNICAL and LNU and involves all other partners.

It will start in January 2024 (M13), following pilot interviews and it will end in June 2024 (M18).

During this period, the 20 national case studies selected - 10 via women-led innovations in farming (WP3a led by UNICAL) and 10 via rural areas (WP3b led by LNU) - will be conducted in each country.

In each national case study, 10 semi-structured in-depth interviews will be conducted with selected women.

Participants will be asked to sign consent forms before they participate in the study (Annex 8). They will be provided with information about the research and the FLIARA project (Annex 7).

With the consent of the respondent, each interview will be recorded. Otherwise, detailed notes will be taken during the interview and complemented right after the interview.

Interviews will be conducted in English or in the national language - it is recommended to use the language most familiar to the person interviewed.

Data management is described in chapter five.

A common interview guide (see Appendix 1) is prepared following the assessment framework to cover all relevant issues and to make sure that national and cross-national comparative analysis will be possible.

During field activities grey literature will be collected (such newsletters, bulletins, fact sheets, reports, project publications, newspaper/magazine articles) related to the specific project/practice. This material will be used in the analysis of the case studies and will be integrated with the information collected in the desktop analysis conducted in T3.1 in relation to the national context.

With the explicit consent of the interviewee, at least one photograph of the location/initiative or of the woman (if in line with the partner National Ethical Application) should be taken to be used in the fact sheet. Video could be recorded, also in connection with the activities envisaged in WP6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, with the explicit consent of the interviewee and if in line with the National Ethical Requirements.

The timing to conduct case studies is January-March 2024.

4.2 INNOVATION AMBASSADOR SELECTION (T3.2)

As part of WP3, twenty women representing a variety of innovations in farming (WP3a) and rural areas (WP3b) across Europe will be selected by project partners to become Innovation Ambassadors (MS3.2) in the FLIARA Community of Practice Networking Events in WP4. This is to promote and sustain female-led and female-engaged enterprise and entrepreneurship.

The selection process will involve national level partners preparing a long list of potential Innovation Ambassadors via the case study work carried out in each country. Each partner will indicate at least 3 potential ambassadors.

UNICAL and LNU will prepare, with the support of the EB, a short-list (20 Innovation Ambassadors) so that a variety of innovations in farming and rural areas are selected.

The selection process will take into consideration both the suitability of the Innovation Ambassador in her area of work as well as her interest in engaging at an international level with the Community of Practice Networking Events and broader communications duties.

The final selection at the national level is then approved by the relevant national level partners.

The selection of Innovation Ambassadors for WP4 is a Milestone (M3) of WP3 and is due by April 2024 (M16).

The timing is:

- Long list prepared by national partners by 31 of March 2024.
- Short-list prepared by UNICAL and LNU, with the support of the EB by 15 of April 2024.
- List approved by partners by 28 of April 2024.

4.3 ASSESSMENT OF CASE STUDIES (T3.3)

The task is led by UNICAL and LNU and involves all other partners.

It will start in January 2024 (M13) and end in June 2024 (M18).

In this task a **pathways analysis on the case study findings** (10 via women-led innovations in farming and 10 via rural areas) will be conducted.

The assessment of case studies therefore should identify, investigate and document the pathways rural women have taken in order to lead a farm or rural innovation.

The aim is to identify the conditions that enable participation and the capacity of females to adopt innovative practices across the different thematic areas. The analysis will provide insights in the background (local context) in which an innovative practice has emerged, the constraints and the favourable conditions that relate to the case, lessons learned, the impact of the innovation on rural areas and the role that females can play in rural transitions.

The analysis will follow the FLIARA assessment framework (D1.4), which investigate three themes:

- 1) Female-led Innovation Pathways
- 1) Innovation Ecosystems
- 2) Mainstreaming Female-Led Innovation

Each national team will be expected to provide a report on the case studies conducted, which UNICAL and LNU will compile.

Data to be used for the analysis are national data gathered at national level in the desktop analysis of T3.1, grey literature collected during the fieldwork and data collected during the fieldwork (interviews).

According to D7.1, the process of data processing includes anonymising participants as much as possible. If full anonymisation is not possible in the context provided, pseudonymisation will be used. Each partner is responsible for this process, which must also be in line with the approved National Ethical Guidelines.

The table of contents of the case study report is available in Appendix 2 (Case study report on rural innovation) and 3 (Case study report on farm innovation).

Each team leader is responsible to prepare a 1-page fact sheet for each interview resulting in 20 fact sheets for each case study conducted.

The template of the fact sheet is available in Appendix 6.

The timing is as follows:

- 1) Case study reports due by each partner by the 1st of May 2024
- 2) Fact sheets due by each partner by the 1st of May 2024
- 3) UNICAL, LNU and Galway will collect the reports and the fact sheets and prepare the Deliverable 3.3 “Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and 200 Fact Sheets on Female Innovations”.

Outcome

D3.3 “Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and 200 Fact Sheets on Female Innovations” will be submitted in June 2024.

The report will be on the findings of the case study content analysis examining constraints and favourable conditions for female led rural and farm innovation, including 200 clear, concise and user-friendly Fact Sheets (100 for Women-led Innovations in Farming and 100 for Innovative Practices of Women in Rural Areas).

The outcome will also feed into discussions in WP4 Community of Practice Networking events and policy and eco-system development in WP5.

4.4. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE CASE STUDIES BY COUNTRY AND SUSTAINABILITY INNOVATION DIMENSION (T3.4)

The task is led by UNICAL and LNU and involves all other partners.

It will start in September 2023 (M9), and it will end in December 2024 (M24).

During this period, a **comparative analysis** of the issues faced by women innovators both farming and in rural areas will be conducted. The analysis will be articulated through the following three steps:

- 1) Analysis **at country level** of the case studies organised by the four sustainability innovation dimensions (environmental, economic, social and cultural).
Each national team would be responsible for preparing the comparative report at the country level, which will serve as the basis for step two.
- 2) Comparative analysis **within the four macro-regional groupings**.
Teams related to the 4 macro-regions will work together to prepare the comparative report. In each group, a partner will coordinate the work (See table 7).
- 3) Analysis of emerging issues comparing across the four regions to derive **European level insights**. UNICAL, LNU and Galway will conduct this analysis.

Table 7. Partners by macro-regional groups

No	Partner short name	Country	Macro Region	Coordinate
1	GALWAY	Ireland	Atlantic	X
2	TU Delft	Netherland	Atlantic	
3	TEAGASC	Ireland	Atlantic	
4	LWL	Ireland	Atlantic	
5	HNEE	Germany	Atlantic	
1	LNU	Sweden	Nordic Baltic	X
2	UOULU	Finland	Nordic Baltic	
3	JU	Sweden	Nordic Baltic	
4	UTU	Finland	Nordic Baltic	
1	UL	Slovenia	Central and Eastern	X
2	ECOLISE	Belgium/ covering Romania	Central and Eastern	
3	MENDELU	Czechia	Central and Eastern	
4	ELARD	Belgium/covering Romania	Central and Eastern	
1	UNICAL	Italy	Mediterranean	X
2	CE	Spain	Mediterranean	

The table of content of the analysis at the country level and the comparative analysis at the macro-regional level report is available in Appendix 4.

The timing is as follows:

- 1) Analysis reports at country level due by each partner by the 1st of July 2024
- 2) Comparative report at macro-regional level due by the 1st of October 2024
- 3) UNICAL, LNU and Galway will derive European level insights by the 1st of December 2024
UNICAL, LNU and Galway will prepare the deliverable D3.4 and the 10-practice abstract.

Outcomes

Deliverable D3.4: Comparative analysis report will be submitted in December 2024 (M24). This deliverable reports on the case study comparative analysis reflecting insights by macro-region and the European level (T3.4).

Deliverable D3.5: Practice Abstracts – batch 1 will be submitted in December 2024 (M24). This deliverable contains 10 practice abstracts. It is based on the outcomes of the 20 case studies (T3.3) and the comparative analysis of case studies (T3.4).

5. WP3 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The WP3 Data Management Plan (DMP) consists of a general description of the types of data that will be collected and generated, the procedures for accessing the data according to their sensitivity, and the procedure for appropriate ethical data management.

The following section provides an overview of the data that will be produced in WP3. For each task it describes:

- The types of data that will be generated or collected.
- The origin of the data.
- The formats that will be used.
- How the research data will be preserved.
- What parts of the datasets will be made available for re-use.

5.1 DATA MANAGEMENT RESEARCH GUIDELINES AND THEMATIC SELECTION (TASK 3.1)

This section reports on the organization of the data that will be collected and processed in relation to Task 3.1.

Data collection for the inventory prepared to select case studies will include information on the general characteristics of women leading innovative practices/projects in farming and in rural area (including social and professional characteristics), types of projects/initiatives conducted and their impacts on rural areas. Scientific literature in national language (or related to the national contexts), grey literature and material published online (e.g. on websites) are the main sources for the preparation of the dataset.

Furthermore, statistical open databases, scientific literature in national language and grey literature, and websites are the main sources for the data generated for the desktop analysis.

The objective is to identify women leading innovation in farming and in rural areas and to collect information on the national context in relation to farming, rural economy, women networks, policy supporting women entrepreneurs, national rural context.

Table 8. Data *T3.1 description

Data collected/Generated	Statistical data and scientific literature in national languages or related to national contexts, grey literature (such as reports and newspaper articles) on women leading innovations in farming and rural areas
Sources	Published literature research; statistical open databases (EUROSTAT, National Statistical data); data open sources available at European and national level; websites are the main sources for the research data.
Format	Documents text (.docx + .pdf+ .txt).
Accessibility	The majority of data sources are publicly available; materials used will not be published in any open-access data repository. Data processed and literature reviewed will be available through the analysis of D3.2 “Inventory of female-led innovation” and Deliverable 3.3 “Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and 200 Fact Sheets on Female Innovations “(data on the national context background). The deliverables can be accessed on the project website.
Usefulness	The information provided in these deliverables will be particularly useful for women considering innovations on farms or in rural areas, actors involved in research and innovation on rural development and on gender issues in rural areas (researchers, practitioners and policy makers).
Re-use	The written analysis of the data will include clear citations and references, so that information can be reused for comparative purposes.

5.2 DATA MANAGEMENT CASE STUDIES AND ASSESSMENT (TASK 3.2- TASK 3.3)

This section reports on the organization of the data that will be collected and processed in relation to Task 3.2. and T3.3.

Using the case-study approach, part of the data will be collected through external databases (grey literature, on-line evidence); the most relevant part will be generated as primary data gathered through qualitative research techniques (in-depth interviews).

The aim is to conduct case studies on innovative practices/project led by women in farming and rural areas and make a pathways analysis of case studies.

Table 9. Data *T3.2-T3.3 description

Data collected/Generated	grey literature, on-line evidence
Sources	Open sources available at national level
Format	documents text (.docx + .pdf+ .txt).
Accessibility	Although the majority of types of source data are publicly available, materials used will not be provided in any open access data repository. Data processed will be available in the Deliverable 3.3 “Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and 200 Fact Sheets on Female Innovations”. The report can be accessed on the FLIARA website and on CORDIS portal.
Usefulness	The information provided in these deliverables will be particularly useful for women considering innovations on farms or in rural areas, actors involved in research and innovation on rural development and gender issues in rural areas (researchers, practitioners and policy makers
Re-use	The written analysis of the data will include clear citations and references to its source, so that information can be reused for comparative purposes.

Table 10. Primary Data *T3.2- T3.3 description

Data collected/Generated	Primary data regarding experiences, practices, point of views and lifestyle of women
Sources	Recordings, transcriptions and notes from 200 women semi-structured in-depth interviews, photos, videos
Format	Audio and video recording; photos and documents text (.mp3 + mp4 + .jpg + .docx + .pdf+ .xlsx).
Accessibility	Only each country’s research team will have access to recordings, transcriptions and minutes of their country case studies. Access will be restricted, due to privacy concerns and potentially sensitive issues, but also because of the difficulty of making data completely anonymous. Analysis and interpretation of primary data will be accessible in the Deliverable 3.3 “Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and 200 Fact Sheets on Female Innovations”. The Deliverable can be accessed on the FLIARA website and on CORDIS website.

	<p>Moreover, the outcomes of each interview will be presented in a 1-page fact sheet (comprised in D3.3). Photos (for which a specific consent form will be asked) can be included in the fact sheets. Only videos (for which a specific consent form will be asked) for communications purpose will be available on the project website and can be used in the WP4 and WP5 meetings and in WP6 otherwise only each country research team will have access to the recordings.</p> <p>The outcomes of the analysis will also be disseminated in open-access scientific publications.</p>
Usefulness	<p>The information provided in this deliverable will be particularly useful for women considering innovations on farms or in rural areas, actors involved in research and innovation on rural development and gender issues in rural areas (researchers, practitioners and policy makers)</p>
Re-use	<p>Data contained in the report could be reused for comparison purposes or being subject to successive different analyses and interventions concerning the role played by women in promoting innovation in farming and rural areas.</p>

5.3 DATA MANAGEMENT COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS (TASK 3.4)

This section reports on the organisation of the data that will be collected and processed in relation to Task 3.4.

Comparative analysis, based on the results of case studies (T3.2 and T3.3), will process data at a higher level of abstraction and interpretation.

Results of analysis and interpretation will be publicly accessible through the Deliverable D3.4 – Comparative analysis report.

Furthermore, the outcomes of the 20 case studies and the comparative analysis will be disseminated also through Deliverable D3.5 – Practice Abstracts – batch 1.

Table 11. Data *T3.4 description

Data collected/Generated	Analysis of primary data and secondary data collected in T 3.1, T3.2 and T3.3
Sources	Primary and secondary data collected and processed in T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3
Format	Text (.docx + .txt + .pdf)
Accessibility	Analysis and interpretation of these data sets will be publicly accessible through the Deliverable D3.4, disseminated in scientific publications open

	access and through Deliverable D3.5 – Practice Abstracts- batch 1. The Deliverables will be available on the FLIARA website and on CORDIS
Usefulness	The information provided in the Report and the Practice abstract will be useful especially for women considering innovations on farms or in rural areas, actors working on research and innovation related to rural development (researchers, practitioners and policy makers).
Re-use	The written analysis of the data will include clear citations and references to its source, so that information can be reused for comparative purposes

6. WP3 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 PROCEDURES AND CRITERIA USED TO IDENTIFY RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

Research participants in WP3 are identified and selected according to their professional capacity, expertise and experiences in leading innovative practices/projects in farming and rural areas. The selection approach followed a clear process. The women selected are considered innovative in relation to a specific sustainability dimension (environmental, economic, social, cultural) and operating in a specific type of rural areas (remote rural area, rural villages, rural area near to city).

A list of potential interviewees was prepared. The list includes two options for each sustainability dimension/rural typology, so that the researchers have a second option for each sustainability dimension/ type of rural area if the first women selected are not available. Women were selected on the basis of their professional capacity, expertise and experiences.

Minors and women who may have any difficulty in giving conscious consent to participation will not be involved in the study. Similarly, migrant women who do not have regular documents to reside in the EU will not be involved, due to their vulnerable position.

However, since communities in rural areas are not homogeneous entities, societal and individual differences are taken into account both for methodological reasons, and in order to avoid unfair exclusion.

Any element defining particular social positions/roles of potential vulnerability in rural areas (as, for example, ethnic and cultural diversity; economic disadvantages) or societal and individual differences (as, for example, family status, community roles, ages) are taken into account in the selection of interviewees and in the analysis.

Women selected for interviews will not be placed in situations where there is a likelihood of physical, mental or emotional harm. Any potential risk will be documented, explained and addressed.

In the event of an unforeseen situation, e.g. regarding the spread of COVID-19, the researchers involved in the interview are obliged to strictly follow the safety instructions in force in the country where the research is conducted.

6.2 INFORMED CONSENT PROCEDURES

As stated in the Ethic Requirements (D8.1 H-POPOD-Requirement No.1), all participants will be informed about the nature and the purpose of the research and innovation activities of the project (See Appendix 7 “Project Information Sheet”).

They will be asked to sign an informed consent form, also for photos and videos (See Appendix 8 “Informed Consent Form”) in order to ensure compliance with ethical standards and guarantee their free and fully informed participation. For photos and videos, national ethical requirements must be taken into account and the informed consent form can be adapted accordingly.

The consent forms will be translated into the languages of the countries where the research and innovation activities will be performed.

The following information will be provided to the participants before they participate in interviews:

- Give participants a clear explanation of the aims, overall purpose, methods and implications of the research.
- Explain the voluntary nature of participation.
- Remind participants that they have a right to withdraw their consent at any time without any consequences.
- Explain the degree of benefit, risks, burden or discomfort involved in participation. Give an estimate of the time and effort expected of participants.
- Explain who is funding the research and for what purpose.
- Disclose who will benefit from the research.
- Give a firm commitment to protecting respondents’ anonymity and privacy (provided that this can genuinely be guaranteed).
- Make a clear commitment to treating personal and sensitive information confidentially.
- Reassure participants that there are security procedures for analysing any data gathered.
- Explain clearly who will have access to any data that participants provide.
- Consider any unintended/unexpected/incidental findings and explain how you intend to deal with such findings.
- Explain briefly where research findings will be published.
- Offer to provide respondents with further information about research if they ask for it.

- Give the name and contact details of the contact person who can answer any queries participants may have.
- Clarify possible uses to which data may be put in future (if this is envisaged) and clarify whether participants will be asked for consent again if this is the case. Cover any issues relating to copyright of data and other materials used in the research.

Before the start of the interview (or other activities) the subject will be asked if these conditions are clear and acceptable, and if yes, the subject will be asked to sign the informed consent form.

6.3 PROCESSING AND MANAGEMENT OF PERSONAL DATA

Although it is not planned or expected that participants will share sensitive personal data (political opinions, religious and philosophical beliefs, etc.), all data collected in the qualitative research activities of WP3 will be treated confidentially, and information collected from participants will be kept confidential, unless the participant gives explicit consent to be quoted.

As for semi-structured in-depth interviews, each interview will be audio recorded only with the consent of the interviewees, otherwise detailed notes will be kept during the interview and complemented right after.

As for transcripts and reports of in-depth interviews, these data will be considered as containing personal information as the in-depth nature of the interview will provide a “fingerprint” of a unique combination of qualities that make the respondents identifiable even if the names are replaced by a code (which we will do).

This data will be handled only for the aims that they are collected, clearly indicated in informed-consent declarations by participants. Data processing will ensure that personal data will be only processed for the aim it is collected and that data processing will stay within the informed consent of the respondent.

Photos of the location/initiative/woman and videos will only be taken with the consent of the interviewees, and only if in line with the National Ethical Approval. Videos recordings for communication purposes will be handled as containing personal data about people’s professional opinion.

Personal data will be pseudonymised and anonymised by removing any identifiable information. Access to these data will be limited to the national research team.

7. FAIR DATA

Findability

In accordance with D7.1 Data Management Plan WP3 data from interviews will be recorded (e.g. MP3, .wav), and transcribed (text e.g. Word). This data will only be shared within the national research team.

All data files shall be named using the following elements in the file name:

- Date: YYYYMMDD
- Descriptive file name
- Initials of the person who last modified the file

Accessibility

In accordance with D.7.1 Data Management Plan all primary data will be retained for at least seven years (4 years post Project as defined in the Joint Controller Agreement) on the servers of the project partner responsible for gathering this new data for the purposes of validation.

Access to new data (including transcripts of interviews) for the validation of the results will be possible under strict access conditions. The responsible project partners will ensure access upon request is solely for this purpose and in line with ethical requirements.

Access will only be granted on the basis of a positive review by the Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) of the partner holding the data and, if there is no HREC at that partner, on the basis of a positive review by the HREC of the coordinator.

Each partner will ensure that there will be people in place to be the curators of the data during this period. The servers for storing the primary data will have password protection and restricted access only to the project partner.

Interoperability

Not relevant for WP3 data

Re-usability

Data consists of generally accepted formats. Most of the data will be qualitative. Transcripts and content coding is expected to be in .docx format., .pdf-files.

Formats are based on open standards to enable data reuse, interoperability and sharing. Access to data (including transcripts of interviews) for the validation of the results will be possible under strict access conditions. The responsible project partners will ensure access upon request for this purpose based on a review by the HREC.

Allocation of Resources

The project partner responsible for keeping the data will support eventual costs for archiving.

Data Security

In accordance with D.7.1 Data Management Plan “Documentation (...) will be securely stored on the Sharepoint server for up to 4 years after the completion of the project. (...) Data gathered during the project can also be securely stored in the partner organisations own trusted data repositories (password protected and encrypted) by the partner responsible for collecting the data. (...) However, where facilities are not available in partner organisations, partners will cooperate in their regional groupings to ensure these requirements are met (as defined in the DoA).”

Interviewers will upload audio files (of interviews), text files of transcriptions/notes and photos/videos at least once per working day to a secure data server. “If in a remote rural context of a specific case study no workable safe connection to the server is available, this upload can be postponed for a few days until such a connection becomes available”

In the event of accidental loss of documents, all partners will follow best practice, which states that researchers should keep three copies of their data, two on different media and one off-site.

More information on the procedures that have to be followed to ensure data security is clearly developed in D7.1 “Data management Plan”, in D8.1 “H-POPD-Requirement No. 1” and in National Ethical Approval.

Only personnel working on the project have access to data files. Responsible for data access at each institution are the following persons:

PARTNER	PERSONNEL
Galway	Maura Farrell
TU Delft	Willem Korthals Altes
TEAGASC	Anne Kinsella
UNICAL	Silvia Sivini
LWL	Tara Farrell
UTU	Tuomas Kuhmonen
UL	Barbara Lampič
CE	Michelle Perello
HNEE	Susanne von Münchhausen
ELARD	Marion Eckardt
UOULU	Simo Sarkki
ECOLISE	Eamon O Hara; Anastasia Oprea
MENDELU	Milada Stastna
LNU	Annie Roos
HLK	Helene Ahl

ANNEX 1. INTERVIEW GUIDELINES

The interview guidelines provide direction on how to conduct the interviews in WP3 and are designed to cover the information asked for the country report case studies and the comparative analysis.

This is not a prescriptive interview format as we will carry out semi structured interviews. This means that the order of the questions, and the question itself may vary with each interviewee. The dialogue among the researcher and the interviewees can meander around the topics indicated in the interview guide - rather than adhering slavishly to verbatim questions as in a standardized survey - and may delve into totally unforeseen issues, that would be useful in the analysis if we find something that we have not already considered.

The two interview guidelines take into account the specificities of rural innovation (Annex1.1) and farm innovation (Annex 1.2).

The guide is organised into 6 sections. For each section a concise comment explains what we have to collect. The question examples cover all topics to be included in the case study report. If different questions are asked, please be aware that all topics must be investigated.

It is suggested to contact the interviewee with either a phone call or by e-mail. In many countries, for example, an e-mail followed by a phone call will usually secure access. Briefly explain what the project is about (you can send the leaflet of the project and refer also to the FLIARA web site) and ask if she would be interested in taking part in the study.

Schedule a day and time, preferably at their place, and send the interviewee an e-mail in advance with the Project Information Sheet and the Consent Form. Please let them know that we are very grateful for their participation.

Prepare for the interview by reading the content of the case study report and the interview guide carefully and determine if you want to change the wording, or the order of the questions. Translate the questions to your own language (the translation tool in Word works with many languages) so that you can conduct the interview in your own language.

Once in the formal interview setting, give a short presentation about the project. **Ask the interviewee to fill in the consent form** and ask for permission to make an audio recording of the interview.

If the person does not agree to a recording, you should take notes.

With the consent of the respondents, take at least a photo of the initiative/the location where the innovation take place or the women leading innovation to be used in the Fact Sheets.

At the end of the interview, thank her and remind her that a Fact sheet about her experience will be prepared.

ANNEX 1.1 INTERVIEW GUIDE RURAL INNOVATIONS

Please consider that we have selected the respondents on the basis of a specific sustainability dimension (cultural/environmental/economic or social sustainability). The innovation might be the business/practice/project itself or specific activities implemented by women. Please, consider that the interview after a description of the business/practice/project should focus on the innovation implemented.

1. General questions about innovator background and the local context

Comment: synthetic information on her career (studying, professional, volunteering) and on her life (family/partner support/constraint, age, moved from elsewhere/from abroad) may help us to better understand her motivations to start the innovation. Pay attention to sensitive data. Synthetic information on the local context will help us to define better the three typologies of area (remote area, rural villages, remote rural areas). This information will be used to fill Chapter 1, the table in Chapter 2 and paragraph 3.1 of the case study report.

1.1 Brief account of personal experience before being involved on the farm.

For example, *Prompt for* Can you first introduce yourself/tell me a little about your life? (age, education, previous jobs, volunteering, moved from elsewhere/from abroad, etc., family/partner support/constraint)

1.2 Description of the local context: brief outline of the overall situation of the context where the business/project is located/the practice implemented.

For example, *Prompt for* what are the main problems of the area (access to broadband, distance from the city, availability of services - schools, sanitary, mobility).

2. The business/practice/project

Comment: we want to gather information on the business/practice/project to understand how it is organised and managed, and whether any environmental issues have been considered in their choices. Please, consider if the innovation implemented is the business/project/practice itself or specific activities implemented in the business/practice/project. This information will be used to fill Chapter 2 (and the table), paragraph 3.4; 4.4, 4.5 of the case study report.

Description of the business/practice/project: when the business/practice/ project was started; legal form of the business (e.g. individual, company, association), types of production/services, how is managed, environmental awareness, use of technology.

For example, *Prompt for:* can you tell me about your business/project/practice? When did you start? Is it a company, an association or an individual enterprise? What do you produce? Which services do you offer? Any renewable energy facilities (e.g. solar, eolic, etc.)? Have environmental issues influenced the implementation of your project/business/practice? (e.g. in circular economy projects). Have you introduced any technological innovation in the management of your business? What marketing tools do you use? Website, social media, other types of advertising? Do you deal with these directly or who does? Have you had to take specific courses on how to use these tools?

Who works in your business/project/practice (other family members, employees)? What is your role in the business/project/practice? Are any volunteers involved?

3. Origins of the innovation

*Comment: this section is intended to reconstruct the very early steps of the **innovation implemented** (this might be the business/practice/project itself or specific activities implemented): we want to understand what motivates women to initiate the innovation, what seemed to be the main obstacles and the main elements of strength. It is a historical part, and every piece of information must be referred to the past, i.e. to the time when she begins to think about the idea. This stage of historical reconstruction precedes any actual/formal step towards starting innovation, thus outlying a sort of pre-historic time for the innovation. What we will be looking for is how, through which passages and vicissitudes, and overcoming what kind of fears and resistance, an idea of the innovation came out of a specific context, and how the features of that context influenced/conditioned these events.*

3.1 Origins of the idea/motivations: how did the original idea of the innovation come about and what did it consist of (year when the idea of the innovation was first elaborated/discussed); description of the original idea. *This information will be used to fill the paragraph 3.1; 4.3 of the case study report.*

For example, *Prompt for:* What was the main idea behind your innovation, and when did you start thinking about it (mention the specific innovation you're referring to)? Also, were there others involved in this process, and in what year did it all begin?

Your main aspiration was to improve rural lives, address sustainability challenges, respond to emerging crises, search for a new sustainable life, the availability of financial resources or what? Does the innovation fulfill a specific need in the area or does the innovation start on the basis of a personal idea?

Do you feel that being a woman has shaped your motivation?

3.2 Constrains and favorable conditions: what were perceived as the main obstacles and the main favorable conditions to the development of the idea (either at personal and/or contextual level). *This information will be used to fill the paragraph 3.2; 4.3 of the case study report.*

For example, *Prompt for:* Which were (if any) the main obstacles that you have to face in developing your idea? For example, lack of financial resources, lack of skills, difficulties in reconciling work and family and in general related to your personal life (children, partner, domestic work, being a woman or LGBTQ+ or migrant, family oppositions etc.); lack of broad band, lack of information or difficulties in accessing information? Any obstacles on the side of the institutions – local, regional, national? How did you face these obstacles? Do you think that being a woman increased the obstacles you faced? Did you have difficulties in having your role on the project/practice/business recognised?

What (if any) are the main favorable conditions you have taken to develop your idea? For example, did you receive support from your partner/family? Did you have the availability of financial resources, built resources, infrastructure? You have been already integrated in networks that turn useful for the implementation of the innovation? There is a tradition of co-operation in this context that has been useful for you?

4. Decision and Preparatory activities

Comment: this section is dedicated to collecting information on the decision and preparatory activities. We want to understand which are the resources mobilised; networks activated, skillset and expertise needed. In short, we want to understand the innovation ecosystem that is supportive towards specific innovations and possible forms of scaling in and scaling down. This information will be used to fill paragraphs 3.3; 4.1, 4.2, 5.9 of the case study report.

For example, *Prompt for:* Which decisions did you have to take and what you have done to transform your idea in reality? Did you have to seek financial resources, built resources? Did you establish networks (with whom) and for what? Did you have access to other family resources (e.g. from family members)?

If you receive financial incentives? From whom? If not, why? In your opinion is access to financial resources viable? Did you have access to other external resources (e.g. from crowdfunding)? [*scaling down*]

Did you receive support from government policies/regulations or local institutions? If yes which support? (For example, technical support, training). If not, why?

Did you need to develop specific skills?

Did you receive support to improve skills/knowledge from organisations/institutions? [*scaling in*]

5. Concretisation of Innovations

Comment: this section is dedicated to collecting information on the tangible outcomes of the innovations. We want to understand whether they manifest as economic, technological, social, cultural, environmental, or institutional changes, or a combination of these dimensions. We have selected them in relation to a specific sustainability dimension on the basis of a desk analysis, but we need to verify on the ground what emerges. If the innovation is the business/practice/project itself, we may have already gathered this information in point 2 (the business/project/practice). This information will be used to fill the paragraph 3.4 and chapter 2 of the case study report.

For example, *Prompt for:* Concretely, what results has the implementation of the innovation brought to your business/project/practice? (e.g. new jobs created, value added processing, tourism services, educational services, use of renewable energy, etc.). Are the achievements mainly economic, social, cultural, environmental or institutional? On which of these areas do they have the greatest impact?

6. Impacts of Innovations

Comment: this section is dedicated to collecting information on the impacts of the innovations on the contexts where they are implemented. Impacts include development towards realization of various dimensions of sustainability, and gender equality. We want to understand if these are incremental (gradual continuous improvements to gender equality within the region or niche), disruptive (novel norms, governance arrangements or on the ground practices that are quickly mainstreamed changing the rural context

towards gender equality), sustaining (significant improvement that helps to sustain gender equality in specific rural region or niche) or radical (breakthrough innovations fundamentally questioning the patriarchal 'normal', but due that facing resistance and blocked by negative resilience.). We also want to understand the impacts of innovations in terms of mainstreaming. This information will be used to fill paragraphs: 3.5; 5.6; 5.7; 5.10 of the case study report.

Concretely, what effects has the implementation of the innovation brought to the local context? (e.g. new services for the community, any institutional changes, etc.)?

Did you collaborate with male colleagues, and did their interactions with you change over time? Has your innovation affected how people view women's roles in rural areas? What emotional challenges did you experience while implementing the innovation?

Do you think that your way of innovating can contribute to changing society's values and behaviour in relation to gender equality? If yes, at what level (local, regional, national)? Are there any actions you consider useful to promote these changes? [*scaling deep*]

In your opinion, which changes in policies/regulations or actions of local institutions would you suggest at different levels to support women rural innovation? (e.g. more incentives, trainings, capacity-building, other).

Have there been any changes in laws/policies/regulations or institutions that have been determined by the innovative work done by women in rural areas? Or has there been/is there a public debate on the role of women in rural areas? [*scaling up*]

Do you plan to expand your activity/project or replicate it elsewhere in the coming years; do you plan to initiate new collaborations to improve your activity/project? If yes, with whom? (e.g. collaboration with training institutions, with industrial organisations, with professional organisations, with other actors in your sector; with other organisations or local networks). Have others been inspired by the innovations you have implemented? Do you know if anyone else has developed a similar innovation elsewhere? Have you helped others to replicate the innovation? If so, who? Have people from outside the area shown interest in the implemented innovation (e.g. people visiting the company, journalists, researchers, etc.)? [*scaling out*].

If you are not intending to expand your innovation or project, why do you choose not to expand or replicate your activity or project elsewhere? Is it due to specific obstacles, and if so, what are they? Alternatively, are you satisfied with the current level of your innovation? How do you assess the capacity of organisations/institutions to provide and support women-led rural innovation? Do you think your innovative work has changed the practices and/or values of these organisations/institutions with respect to how they support women in particular? [*scaling in*]

ANNEX 1.2 INTERVIEW GUIDE FARM INNOVATIONS

Please consider that we have selected the respondents on the basis of a specific sustainability dimension (cultural/environmental/economic or social sustainability). The innovation might be the farm itself or specific activities implemented in the farm by women. Please, consider that the interview after a description of the farm should focus on the innovation implemented.

1. General questions about innovator background and the local context

Comment: synthetic information on her career (studying, professional, volunteering) and on her life (family/partner support/constraint, age, moved from elsewhere/from abroad) may help us to better understand her motivations to start the innovation. Pay attention to sensitive data. Synthetic information on the local context will help us to define better the three typologies of area (remote area, rural villages, remote rural areas). This information will be used to fill Chapter 1, the table in Chapter 2 and paragraph 3.1 of the case study report.

1.1 Brief account of personal experience before being involved in the farm.

For example, *Prompt for* Can you first introduce yourself/tell me a little about your life? (age, education, previous jobs, volunteering, moved from elsewhere/from abroad, etc., family/partner support/constraint)

1.2 Description of the local context: brief outline of the overall situation of the context where the farm is located.

For example, *Prompt for:* what are the main problems of the area (access to broadband, distance from the city, availability of services - schools, sanitary, mobility)

2. The farm

Comment: we want to gather information on the farm to understand how it is organised and managed, and whether any environmental issues have been considered in their choices. Please, consider if the innovation implemented on the farm (is the farm itself or specific activities implemented on the farm). This information will be used to fill Chapter 2 (and the table), paragraph 3.4, 4.4, 4.5 of the case study report.

Description of the farm: when she started farming; information on Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) owned/leased, legal form of the farm (one person / family / community), types of production, style of farming (peasant versus entrepreneurship; organic versus conventional agriculture), multifunctional aspects; product processing, environmental awareness, use of technology.

For example, *Prompt for:* can you tell me about your farm? When did you start farming? What is your role on the farm? Is it a family farm or a company? The land structure is concentrated or dispersed? How many hectares does the farm cover?

What does it produce? Is the production certified (e.g. organic, biodynamic) or does it have a label of origin (e.g. PDO, PGI, Slow Food Presidium).

Did you process products? Which services are offered by the farm (e.g. tourism or cultural activities, social farming, educational, etc.).

Any renewable energy facilities (e.g. solar, eolic, etc.)? Have environmental issues influenced the way of farming? [*If applicable*] why did you choose to farm organic/biodynamic/agro-ecological?

Have you introduced any technological innovation in the management of your farm? What marketing tools do you use? Website, social media, other types of advertising? Do you deal with these directly or who does? Have you had to take specific courses on how to use these tools?

Who works on the farm (other family members, farm workers)?

3. Origins of the innovation

Comment: this section is intended to reconstruct the very early steps of the innovation implemented in the farm (this might be the farm itself or specific activities implemented in the farm): we want to understand what motivates women to initiate the innovation, what seemed to be the main obstacles and the main elements of strength. It is a historical part, and every piece of information must be referred to the past, i.e. to the time when she begins to think about the idea. This stage of historical reconstruction precedes any actual/formal step towards starting innovation, thus outlying a sort of pre-historic time for the innovation. What we will be looking for is how, through which passages and vicissitudes, and overcoming what kind of fears and resistance, an idea of the innovation came out of a specific context, and how the features of that context influenced/conditioned these events.

3.1 Origins of the idea/motivations: how did the original idea of the innovation come about and what did it consist of (year when the idea of the innovation was first elaborated/discussed); description of the original idea. *This information will be used to fill the paragraph 3.1; 4.3 of the case study report.*

For example, *Prompt for:* What was the main idea behind your innovation, and when did you start thinking about it (mention the specific innovation you're referring to)? Also, were there others involved in this process, and in what year did it all begin?

Your main aspiration was to improve farming, rural lives, address sustainability challenges, respond to emerging crises, search for a new sustainable life, the availability of financial resources/farmland or what? Does the innovation fulfill a specific need in the area or in the farm or does the innovation start on the basis of a personal idea? Do you feel that being a woman has shaped your motivation?

3.2 Constrains and favorable conditions: what were perceived as the main obstacles and the main favorable conditions to the development of the idea (either at personal and/or contextual level). *This information will be used to fill the paragraph 3.2; 4.3 of the case study report.*

For example, *Prompt for:* Which were (if any) the main obstacles that you have to face in developing your idea? For example, lack of financial resources, lack of skills, lack of land, difficulties in reconciling work and family and in general related to your personal life (children, partner, domestic work, being a woman or LGBTQ+ or migrant, family oppositions etc.); lack of broadband, lack of information or difficulties in accessing information? Any obstacles on the side of the institutions – local, regional, national? How did you face these obstacles? Do you think that being a woman increased the obstacles you faced? Did you have difficulties in having your role on the farm recognised?

What (if any) are the main favorable conditions you have taken to develop your idea? For example, did you receive support from your partner/family? Did you have the availability of land, financial resources, infrastructure? You have been already integrated in networks that turn useful for the implementation of the innovation? There is a tradition of co-operation in this context that has been useful for you?

4. Decision and Preparatory activities

Comment: this section is dedicated to collecting information on the decision and preparatory activities. We want to understand which are the resources mobilised; networks activated, skillset and expertise needed. In short, we want to understand the

innovation ecosystem that is supportive towards specific innovations and possible forms of scaling in and scaling down. This information will be used to fill paragraphs 3.3; 4.1, 4.2, 5.9 of the case study report.

For example, *Prompt for:* Which decisions did you have to take and what you have done to transform your idea in reality? Did you have to seek financial resources, built resources? Did you establish networks (with whom) and for what? Did you have access to other family resources (e.g. from family members; availability of the family farm)?

If you receive financial incentives? From whom? If not, why? In your opinion is access to financial resources viable? Did you have access to other external resources (e.g. from crowdfunding, from consumers)? [*scaling down*]

Did you receive support from government policies/regulations or local institutions? If yes which support? (For example, technical support, training). If not, why?

Did you need to develop specific skills?

Did you receive support to improve skills/knowledge from organisations/institutions? Did you get support from AKIS – (Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System) or are somehow involved in it, or are you aware of the AKIS model? [*scaling in*]

5. Concretisation of Innovations

Comment: this section is dedicated to collecting information on the tangible outcomes of the innovations. We want to understand whether they manifest as economic, technological, social, cultural, environmental, or institutional changes, or a combination of these dimensions. We have selected them in relation to a specific sustainability dimension on the basis of a desk analysis, but we need to verify on the ground what emerges. If the innovation is the farm itself, we may have already gathered this information in point 2 (the farm). This information will be used to fill the paragraph 3.4 and chapter 2 of the case study report.

For example, *Prompt for:* Concretely, what results has the implementation of the innovation brought to the farm? (e.g. new jobs created, value added processing, tourism services, educational services, use of renewable energy or sustainable agriculture productions, agrobiodiversity conservation, etc.).

Are the achievements mainly economic, social, cultural, environmental or institutional? On which of these areas do they have the greatest impact?

6. Impacts of Innovations

Comment: this section is dedicated to collecting information on the impacts of the innovations on the contexts where they are implemented. Impacts include development towards realization of various dimensions of sustainability, and gender equality. We want to understand if these are incremental (gradual continuous improvements to gender equality within the region or niche), disruptive (novel norms, governance arrangements or on the ground practices that are quickly mainstreamed changing the rural context towards gender equality), sustaining (significant improvement that helps to sustain gender equality in specific rural region or niche) or radical (breakthrough innovations fundamentally questioning the patriarchal 'normal', but due that facing resistance and blocked by negative resilience.). We also want to understand the impacts of innovations

in terms of mainstreaming. This information will be used to fill paragraphs: 3.5; 5.6; 5.7; 5.10 of the case study report.

Concretely, what effects has the implementation of the innovation brought to the local context? (e.g. new services for the community, a different way of procuring food, any institutional changes, etc.)?

Did you collaborate with male colleagues, and did their interactions with you change over time? Has your innovation affected how people view women's roles in agriculture? What emotional challenges did you experience while implementing the innovation?

Do you think that your way of innovating can contribute to changing society's values and behaviour in relation to gender equality? If yes, at what level (local, regional, national)? Are there any actions you consider useful to promote these changes? [*scaling deep*]

In your opinion, which changes in policies/regulations or actions of local institutions would you suggest at different levels to support women farm innovation? (e.g. more incentives, trainings, capacity-building, other).

Have there been any changes in laws/policies/regulations or institutions that have been determined by the innovative work done by women in agriculture? Or has there been/is there a public debate on the role of women in agriculture? [*scaling up*]

Do you plan to expand your activity/project or replicate it elsewhere in the coming years; do you plan to initiate new collaborations to improve your activity/project? If yes, with whom? (e.g. collaboration with training institutions, with industrial organisations, with professional organisations, with other actors in your sector; with other organisations or local networks). Have others been inspired by the innovations you have implemented? Do you know if anyone else has developed a similar innovation elsewhere? Have you helped others to replicate the innovation? If so, who? Have people from outside the area shown interest in the implemented innovation (e.g. people visiting the company, journalists, researchers, etc.)? [*scaling out*].

If you are not intending to expand your innovation or project, why do you choose not to expand or replicate your activity or project elsewhere? Is it due to specific obstacles, and if so, what are they? Alternatively, are you satisfied with the current level of your innovation? How do you assess the capacity of organisations/institutions to provide and support women-led agricultural innovation? Do you think your innovative work has changed the practices and/or values of these organisations/institutions with respect to how they support women in particular? What do you think of the AKIS services (Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System)? Do you think it can support women in particular? *How do you think it could be improved to include more women?* [*scaling in*]

ANNEX 2. INDEX CASE STUDIES REPORT ON RURAL INNOVATION

In-depth interviews should be transcribed. Since data will be collected in the context of a specific case study, it will be difficult to render them completely anonymous. However, only the national research team will see the detailed notes and transcriptions.

Published reports and conclusions will all be on a higher level of analysis, and no direct quotes or references to specific persons will be included, unless the informant involved provides explicit consent.

The following structure for the case study report is articulated in paragraphs, with the specification of their content. Sub-paragraphs should be avoided in order to keep the structure simple and versatile.

1. The National Context.

We “need to provide insights into the background (local context) from which an innovative practice has emerged” (GA). You may use the desktop analysis data conducted in T3.1 and any other information on the local context collected during the interview highlighting the characteristic of the 3 different typologies of area (remote area, rural villages, remote rural areas).

2. The Innovation

Which are the innovations analysed? Consider presenting the innovation by highlighting the main sustainability dimension it refers to and the typology of area.

Fill the following table:

N. Interview	Age	Educational Level	Legal form of the business/enterprises	Year when it started

3. Innovation Pathways

3.1 *Motivators for Innovation*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis. Consider also if individual professional and life stage has been a catalyst or not for their motivations.

Include what motivates women to initiate an innovation in a rural context?

Do they have an aspiration to improve rural lives, address sustainability challenges, respond to emerging crises, search for a new sustainable life, or what? Is there a mismatch between reality and their vision of desirable futures? Does the innovation fulfill a specific need in the area or does the innovation start on the basis of a personal idea or a personal need (for example, financial viability)?

3.2 *Constrains and favourable conditions.*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

What are the constraints and what are the favorable conditions for women leading innovations in rural areas?

For example, personal constraints (e.g. family status, children, lack of financial resources, lack of skills) or context constraints (e.g. lack of broad band, lack of information/training/difficulties in accessing information). How these constraints were faced?

For example, personal favorable conditions (e.g. great networking capacity, partner support, etc.), context favorable conditions (e.g. availability of financial resources; availability of infrastructure).

3.3 Idea and Preparations / Decisions and Preparatory Activities

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis. Consider also if individual professional and life stage has influenced this stage of the innovation pathways.

Which decisions they have taken and what they have done to transform their motivation in reality. Which were their preparatory activities? For example, did they have to seek financial resources, for built resources, did they have networks (at which level) for what? Did they need skill building?

3.4 Concretisation of Innovations

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

Which are the tangible outcomes of these innovations at the level of the practice/project? For example, new jobs created, new products or services, use of renewably energy, etc. The outcomes manifest as economic, technological, social, cultural, environmental, or institutional changes, or a combination of these dimensions?

3.5 Impacts of Innovations

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

What effects did the innovations have on the places where they were introduced (consider the contribution to gender equality and rural development)?

Can the innovations be considered incremental, sustaining, radical, or disruptive innovations?

4. Innovation ecosystems

4.1 Political.

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

How do political decisions impact the motivations, opportunities, and challenges for women entrepreneurs in rural settings? Did they receive support from government policies/regulations or local institutions? Have local policies/regulations or institutions hindered them? What changes in policies/regulations or action by local institutions are suggested?

4.2 Economic

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

Did they receive financial incentives? From whom? If not, why? Is access to financial resources viable? Have they had access to other external resources (e.g. crowdfunding)?

4.3 Social

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

How do social factors, like cultural norms, gender roles, community support, and social networks influence the motivations and challenges faced by women involved in rural innovations? Are they engaged/active at community level? Do they participate in networking locally, regionally and/or nationally?

4.4 *Technological*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

Did they use or develop particular technologies to develop innovation? Which ones? Do technological advances enable or limit women-led innovations in rural areas? Does the availability of technology, digital infrastructure, communication tools and access to information support women-led innovation paths? In what way?

4.5 *Environmental*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

Do environmental factors (e.g. natural resources, climate conditions, environmental sustainability) influence the type of innovations? Do they address environmental degradation and have ecological consideration in promoting the innovations?

5. Mainstreaming actions

5.1 *Scaling up*

Have laws, policies, institutions or norms changed or begun to change as a result of women's innovative actions? Which innovations have had this impact? What would be needed to foster this impact?

5.2 *Scaling out*

Has there been a geographical replication or a widening of the range or scope of innovation? For which innovations? Are there women collaborating with local communities/institutions or single actors to replicate and adapt their innovation in other rural contexts? Where/With whom? Is it possible to assume, given the positive results achieved by women, that these may influence others and that innovations may spread in this way? What actions do they think would be useful to foster this dissemination?

5.3 *Scaling down*

Have women received technical support, funding or participated in capacity building programmes? If yes, from whom and in relation to which innovation? If not, why?

5.4 *Scaling In*

Do women innovators value the capacity of organizations/institutions to provide and support women-led rural innovations? Have they received support to improve skills/knowledge from organisations/institutions? What advisory service would be useful to support them? Have they fostered a change in the practices/values of these organisations/institutions? What actions do they think would be useful to foster this change?

5.5 *Scaling Deep*

Do their actions contribute/have they contributed to changing societal values and behaviour in relation to gender equality? There have been changes in the dominant view of women in rural areas. Have contributed to fundamentally challenging patriarchal 'normality'? If yes, at what level (local, regional, national)? What actions do they think would be useful to foster this change.

ANNEX 3. INDEX CASE STUDIES REPORT ON FARMS INNOVATION

1. The National Context

We “need to provide insight in the background (local context) from which an innovative practice has emerged” (GA). You may use the desktop analysis data conducted in T3.1 and any other information on the local context collected during the interview highlighting the characteristic of the 3 different typology of area (remote area, rural villages, remote rural areas).

In addition, add a synthetic and clear overview of the agricultural sector in the country (e.g. number of farms, female farm managers, average farm size). You may use the desktop analysis data conducted in T3.1.

2. The Innovation

Which is the innovation analysed? Consider presenting the innovation highlighting the main sustainability dimension and the typology of area.

Fill the following table:

N.Inter view	Age	Educational Level	Dimension of the farm (ha)	Property rights (own; rented)	Legal form of the farm (family farmer; company)	Year when she started operating in the farm

3. Innovation Pathways

3.1 *Motivators for Innovation*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis. Consider also if individual professional and life stage has been a catalyst or not for their motivations.

Include what motivates women to initiate innovation in farming.

Do they have aspirations for improving farming, rural lives, addressing sustainability challenges, responding to emerging crises, searching for a new sustainable life, or what? Is there a mismatch between reality and their vision of desirable futures? Does the innovation fulfill a specific need in the area/ in the farm or does the innovation start on the basis of a personal idea, or need?

3.2 *Constrains and favourable conditions.*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

What are the constraints and what are the favorable conditions for women leading innovation in farming.

For example, personal constraints (e.g. family status, children, lack of financial resources, lack of skills, lack of land) or context constraints (e.g. lack of broadband, lack of information/difficulties in accessing information). How these constrains were faced?

For example, personal favorable conditions (e.g. great networking capacity, partner support, availability of the family farm, etc.), context favorable conditions (e.g. availability

of financial resources; availability of infrastructure). How were these favorable conditions taken?

3.2 *Idea and Preparations / Decisions and Preparatory Activities*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis. Consider also if individual professional and life stage has influenced this stage of the innovation pathways.

Which decisions did they make and how did they turn their motivation into reality. What were their preparatory activities? For example, did they seek financial resources, built resources, established networks (at what level) for what? Do they need to develop skills? Do they have access to other family resources (e.g. from family members; availability of the family farm)?

3.4 *Concretisation of Innovations*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

Which are the tangible outcomes of these innovations at the level of the farm? For example, new jobs created, new products or services, use of renewable energy, agrobiodiversity conservations, etc. The outcomes manifest as economic, technological, social, cultural, environmental, or institutional changes, or a combination of these dimensions?

3.5 *Impacts of Innovations*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

What effects did the innovations have on the places where they were introduced? Can innovations be considered incremental, sustaining, radical, or disruptive?

4. Innovation ecosystems

4.1 *Political.*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

How do political decisions impact the motivations, opportunities, and challenges for women farmers? Did they receive support from government policies/regulations or local institutions? Have local policies/regulations or institutions hindered them? What changes in policies/regulations or action by local institutions are suggested?

4.2. *Economic*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

Did they receive financial incentives? From whom? If not, why? Is access to financial resources viable? Have they had access to other external resources (e.g. from crowdfunding, from consumers)

4.3 *Social*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

How social factors (e.g. cultural norms, gender roles, community support, and social networks) shape the motivations and challenges faced by women involved in farming innovations? Are they engaged at community level? Are they networking? Locally/regionally or nationally? Did they have difficulties in having their role on the farm recognised, particularly by any employees?

4.4 *Technological*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

What technology have they used to develop the innovation in the farm? Do technological advances enable or limit women-led innovations in farming? Does the availability of technology, digital infrastructure, communication tools and access to information support women-led innovation paths? In what way? Have they developed a technology? Which one?

4.5 *Environmental*

Consider the typology of the area in the analysis.

Do environmental factors (e.g. natural resources, climate conditions, environmental sustainability) influence the type of innovations? Do they address environmental degradation and have ecological consideration in promoting the innovations? What farming method have they adopted? If they have adopted a sustainable farming method (e.g. agro-ecological, organic, biodynamic approach), why did they make this choice?

5. Mainstreaming action

5.1 *Scaling up.*

Have laws, policies, institutions or norms changed or begun to change as a result of women's innovative actions in farming? Which innovations have had this impact? What would be needed to foster this impact?

5.2 *Scaling out*

Has there been a geographical replication or a widening of the range or scope of innovation? For which innovations? Are there women collaborating with local communities/institutions or single actors to replicate and adapt their innovation in other rural contexts? Where/With who? Is it possible to assume, given the positive results achieved by women, that these may influence others and that innovation may spread in this way? What actions do they think would be useful to foster this dissemination.

5.3 *Scaling down*

Have women received technical support, funding or participated in capacity building programmes/farming programmes? If yes, from whom and in relation to which innovation? If not, why?

5.4 *Scaling In*

Do they value the capacity of organizations/institutions to provide and support women-led farming innovations? Have they received support to improve skills/knowledge from organisations/institutions? Have they fostered a change in the practices/values of these organisations/institutions? What actions do they think would be useful to foster this change? Do they know about AKIS – (Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System)? Do they get support from it or are somehow involved in it?

5.5 *Scaling Deep*

Do their actions contribute/have they contributed to changing societal values and behaviour in relation to gender equality? There have been changes in the dominant view of women and their role in agriculture. Do they have contributed to fundamentally challenging patriarchal 'normality'? If yes, at what level (local, regional, national)? What actions do they think would be useful to foster this change.

ANNEX 4. INDEX COMPARATIVE REPORT

Each report at national level and macro-regional level has the same index.

Farm and rural innovations are included in the same report. However, they are analysed separately. The analysis should consider the sustainability dimensions of the innovations.

We acknowledge that in concrete realities it could be difficult to consider separately the sustainability dimensions in relations to practices/projects but from an analytical point of view, we have considered for each respondent the sustainability dimension that we consider prevalent in relation to the theme and subtheme identified in D1.4 and T3.1.

At macro-regional level also the typology of area should be considered.

1.The macro-regional context (this section is not necessary for the comparative analysis at country level)

Give information on the typology of the area in the countries analysed.

2. Innovation Pathways

2.1 Motivators for Innovation

What motivates woman to initiate innovation in rural and farming context?

Compare the motivation in relation to the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

2.2. Constraints and favourable conditions.

What are the constraints and what are the favorable conditions for women leading Innovation in farming?

Compare the constraints and the favourable conditions in relation to the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

2.3. Idea and Preparations / Decisions and Preparatory Activities

How women act and seek support and resources to implement innovation in rural areas and farming?

Compare what they have done to transform their motivation in reality, also considering if individual professional and life stage has influenced this stage of the innovation pathways. The comparative analysis should be in relation to the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

2.4 Concretisation of Innovations

Which concrete innovations are developed in terms of dimensions of sustainability? Compare innovations and their tangible outcomes. The comparative analysis should be in relation to the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

2.5 Impacts of Innovations

Which are the impacts in terms of rural sustainability and gender equality?

Compare the impacts of innovations considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

3. Innovation ecosystems

3.1 *Political aspects*

How and how well political factors (e.g. government policies, regulations, local institutions) can facilitate or hinder the female led innovations journeys?

Compare how political decisions impact the motivations, opportunities, and challenges for women farmers. In a positive or negative way. Compare if they received any support from government policies/regulations or local institutions. Compare if changes in policies/regulations or action by local institutions are suggested. Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

3.2 *Economic aspects*

How economic conditions influence women's decision to innovate? Which are the economic incentives that can facilitate the expansion of viable female led innovations journey?

Compare if they receive financial incentives. From whom. If not, why. Compare if they had access to other resources (e.g. from family members; availability of family farm; real estate). Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

3.3 *Social aspects*

How and how well social factors (e.g. cultural norms, gender roles, community support, social networks) can facilitate or hinder the female led innovation journeys?

Compare how social factors (e.g. cultural norms, gender roles, community support, and social networks) shape the motivations and challenges faced by women involved in farming and rural innovations. Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

3.4 *Technological aspects*

How and how well technological factors (e.g. availability of technology, digital infrastructure, communication tools and access to information) can facilitate or hinder the female led innovation journeys?

Compare the technology used to develop the innovation in the farm. Compare if the availability of technology, digital infrastructure, communication tools and access to information support women-led innovation paths. Compare if they have developed new technologies. Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

3.5 *Environmental aspects*

How and how well environmental factors (e.g. natural resources, climate conditions, environmental sustainability) influence the type of innovations promoted by women in rural areas and in farming? How and how well women address environmental degradation and protect and improve the natural habitat of rural areas?

Compare if environmental factors (e.g. natural resources, climate conditions, environmental sustainability) influenced the type of innovations? Compare if they adopted a sustainable farming method (e.g. agro-ecological, organic, biodynamic approach)/ a circular economic approach/ energy saving measures why did they make this choice. Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

4. Mainstreaming action

4.1 *Scaling up.*

Has there been a change in laws, policies, institutions or norms that could support women-led innovations? Or can the positive results of women-led innovation support this change?

Compare if any changes or initial changes have been registered. Compare what would be needed to foster this impact. Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

4.2 *Scaling out*

Has there been a geographical replication or a broadening of the range or scope of innovation? Do women collaborate with local communities/organisations to replicate and adapt their innovations to different rural contexts? Or can the positive results of women-led innovation support this diffusion?

Compare if any scaling out has been achieved. Compare actions that would be useful to foster this spread. Compare the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

4.3 *Scaling down.*

Are there capacity-building programmes, funding or technical support for women to implement their innovations locally?

Compare if any scaling down has happened. Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

4.4 *Scaling in*

Do organizations and institutions have the capacity to deliver and support women-led rural innovations? Do advisory services and Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Systems (AKIS) support women-led innovations? Have the practices and values of organizations and institutions been changed by women-led innovations?

Compare if any scaling in has happened (e.g. they received support to improve skills/knowledge from organisations/institutions. They fostered a change in the practices/values of these organisations/institutions). Compare whether any actions have been suggested to foster this change. Compare if they know about AKIS – (Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System), if they get support from it or are somehow involved in it. Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

4.5 *Scaling deep.*

Have societal values and behaviours been changed by women-led innovations in relation to gender equality?

Compare whether there are changes in societal values and behaviours. Compare at what level (local, regional, national). Compare if any actions have been suggested to foster this change. Compare considering the sustainability dimension (and the typology of area at macro-regional level).

ANNEX 5. INSTRUCTION FOR TEXTUAL REFERENCING AND ANNEX TO CASE STUDY

A common system of citing field material within the text is suggested. This should be applied to interviews and Deliverables. The system is based on the organisation of field material in structured lists, where interviews will be numbered and ordered by sustainability dimension and rural area typology.

Interview quotations in the text should be followed by a parenthesis with basic information on:

1. Nation (national code), a letter referred to the typology of case study (R for rural innovation, F for farm); sustainability dimension (E, environmental; S social; C cultural; EC economic) and typology of rural area (1 Rural remote area, 2 rural area close to city, 3 Rural villages)
2. Number of the interview.

For example: “Our practice was started in and was very successful.” (IT_R_C_1/int. 1), where “IT” is ‘Italy’, R is “case-study on Rural innovation”, C is “cultural sustainability dimension”, 1 is in “rural area close to city”, whilst “int. 1” means ‘interview 1’.

Partners will be provided with a table with the Codes for the quotations in relation to the respondents selected.

All the characteristics of the respondent can be found in the structured list of interviews (see table 12). **There should be one for each case study, in the annex.**

Table 12. List of Interview (Template)

Int.n.	Sustainability dimension	Rural Typology	Date of the interview	Other useful information	CODE

ANNEX 6. FACT SHEET TEMPLATE

Short title

Short summary for practitioners on the women led-innovation and on the (final or expected) outcomes (1400-1800 characters, word count – no spaces) of the practice/project. A photo could be included in the Fact sheet.

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- **Description** of the innovation.
- Main tangible **outcomes** of the innovation (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the innovation is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?
- Useful links

The summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using direct and easily understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners. Research-oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

A template will be provided which include different banners color for each sustainability dimension and National Flags:

Flags (to be adapted by Consulta Europa):

Fact Sheet #xx

Your title goes here and here

Elements:

TITLE

Text text text text

Figure 1.

SUBTITLE

Text

Table 1.

SUBTITLE

Text

- Example 1
- Example 2
- Example 3

TEXT SECTION

Text text text

GUIDELINES

Format:

Short summary for practitioners on the women led-innovation and on the (final or expected) outcomes (1400-1800 characters, word count – no spaces) of the practice/project.

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Description of the innovation
- Main tangible outcomes of the innovation (expected or final)
- The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the innovation is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results
- Useful links

Edition:

To edit header/banner on top of the page double click and make sure to click on the typing boxes. Do not move the background banner image. In case you move it. Just make sure to fix it to the initial position (this affects all the pages).

Font: Arial
Minimum Size: 12

To apply styles: Styles section at the home toolbar as below:

ANNEX 7. PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET TEMPLATE

This template should be translated in national language.

Purpose of the research study:

FLIARA is a three-year research and innovation project concerned with exploring in an in-depth way women’s role in a more sustainable rural future. Female innovation and entrepreneurial potential have become an under-exploited source of rural economic growth. To respond to this, the core objective of FLIARA is to ensure that women are embedded in, and supported by, a more effective innovation ecosystem. Using novel research methods, such as futures research, the project aims to spotlight women’s achievements; provide them with a source of inspiration and knowledge; network them with key actors engaged in innovation; heighten their visibility within national and international institutional decision-making contexts and increase their capacity and improve skills to empower women. By developing targeted instruments, strategies and policies that cater for female led innovations, FLIARA will ensure that women can contribute to the overall sustainability of rural areas.

Your participation

You are being approached to participate because you have experience and knowledge that will be of value to the research that we hope you will be willing to share. Your participation in this study involves being participant in an interview/ as part of a case study on women-led innovation in farming/rural area [delete as appropriate]. The interview will involve open discussion around your practice/project [delete as appropriate] and the innovation implemented.

By participating in this research, you will make an important contribution to research and innovation on providing opportunities for women in agriculture and rural areas. There is no financial compensation for your participation in this research. However, before your participation in this study, we would like to inform you that participation is voluntary and to ask you to take your time to read the provided information about this project carefully. You are free to ask as many questions or queries as you like before signing the consent form and entitled to understandable answers at any time before, during, or after your participation in this research. You are also entitled to withdraw from the research at any point that you wish. Please don’t hesitate to ask questions or speak to the Principal Investigator of this study before you decide to participate. Confidentiality and anonymity will be ensured throughout the research. All statements from participants will be anonymised. Participants’ real names will not be used, and no individual will be identified.

14. Contact and other information

PROJECT ACRONYM, TITLE AND NUMBER	FLIARA - Female Led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas (Project: 101084234 — FLIARA — HORIZON-CL6-2022-COMMUNITIES-01)
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<i>Project Duration</i>	3 years
<i>Principal Investigator</i>	[Insert partner details]
<i>Other Investigator</i>	[Insert relevant details]
<i>Research Ethics Office</i>	Email: Phone:
<i>Data Protection Office</i>	Email: Phone:

ANNEX 8. CONSENT FORM TEMPLATE

This template should be translated in national language. Partners may adapt it according to their Ethical Approval.

We would like to invite you to take part in the FLIARA research and innovation project to contribute to an improved understanding of women’s role in a more sustainable rural future. The project seeks to understand the role rural women can play in the future of rural areas, through farming and rural innovative practices. The FLIARA project team aim to carry out a number of case study interviews with a variety of women. The overall aim of the project will be to influence policy and practice for the enhanced engagement of rural women in innovative practices on farms and rural entrepreneurship.

The current case study is undertaken by the [organisation name] FLIARA project. FLIARA is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme, grant no. 101084234. The project started on January 1, 2023, and will continue until the end of 2025.

Before you consent to participate, we would like to ask you to read the Participant Information sheet provided and mark each box below with your initials if you agree. We would also like to inform you that participation in this research is voluntary, and you have the right to decline to answer any question or terminate your involvement at any point during the research interview. Contact details for relevant personnel, if you have any queries or issues, is provided in the Participant Information sheet.

Please initial each statement if you agree:

I confirm that I have read the Participant Information sheet and fully understand what is expected of me in this study.	
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I confirm that I have had the opportunity to ask any questions and to have them answered.	
I understand that my interview will be audio recorded.	
I understand that audio recordings and/or notes taken will be kept until the research project has been examined.	
I understand that there is no compensation for participating in this study.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.	
I understand that my personal data will be kept completely anonymous and will be treated as confidential.	
I understand that once my data has been anonymised and incorporated into themes, it might not be possible for it to be withdrawn, though every attempt will be made to extract my data if requested, up to the point of publication.	
I understand that the information from my interview will be pooled with other participants' responses, anonymised and general conclusions may be published.	
I consent to information and quotations from my interview being used in reports, conferences and training events.	
I understand that any information I give will remain strictly confidential and anonymous unless it is thought that there is a risk of harm to myself or others, in which case the Principal Investigator/Researcher may need to share this information with their research supervisor.	
I confirm that I am an adult	
I consent to take part in the above study	
I consent to generate a Fact Sheet on your practice/project to be used for FLIARA communication purposes.	

I have read the consent form carefully and I understood its content. I choose voluntarily to participate in this research study for the FLIARA project and understand that, if I ask, I will receive a copy of this form. I understand that my consent does not take away any legal rights in the case of negligence or other legal faults of anyone who is involved in this study. I further understand that nothing in this consent form is intended to replace any applicable EU, state, or local laws.

Name of the Participant _____

Organisation _____

Place and Date _____

Signature _____

Name of the Researcher _____

Organisation _____

Place and Date _____

Signature _____

Photography, filming, social media, publicity, and data storage consent form – FLIARA Project

Please complete this form to give consent to the FLIARA Project to take multimedia content (photos and videos) during the **FLIARA project's activities**, which will then be stored and used for FLIARA communication purposes.

Multimedia data will be stored in the FLIARA secured repository and used, with your consent, by the FLIARA consortium to fulfil the necessary communication and dissemination work:

- The video and/or audio recordings and any reproduction shall remain the property of the FLIARA project consortium and may use the image as it sees fit.
- The images may appear publicly as part of the Fact sheets of Women-led innovations, project website, social media communications and/or other promotional materials related to the project.
- The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harms or undue embarrassment to the parties involved.
- The participant's name may appear in a caption in the multimedia material, used in accordance with the above terms, or in the editorial text accompanying it. Also, the multimedia content may be used without any reference to my name.

I do hereby consent to the use by FLIARA Project of my image, video, voice, or all three of them, in the described above purposes. according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):	
Yes	
No	

Name of the Participant _____

Organisation _____

Place and Date _____

Signature _____

Name of the Researcher _____

Organisation _____

Place and Date _____

Signature _____

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Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas

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